

The need for roads in the history of mankind and the emergence of caravan routes as the first communication system

1. Salimov Bakhridin Lutfullaevich. Professor of Tashkent State Transport University.

2. Xudayberdiev Azimjon Uktamovich. Student of Tashkent State Transport University

ANNOTATION

In the article, the term communication is generally used in two directions: first, in road and transport infrastructure; the second is in the field of information systems. It is analyzed that these two areas differ from each other in terms of essence and content, and the role of ancient caravan routes in the formation of human society.

Key words: humanity, road, communication, transport infrastructure, caravan routes.

INTRODUCTION

Information about when humanity appeared on Earth changes from year to year. In the scientific sources of the 1980s, it was written that the time of the appearance of the first people was 2.5 - 3 million years. Before any time had passed, these numbers changed twice. Until now, the remains of people who are considered

the most ancient were found in the Aramis River basin in northern Ethiopia in 1994. The age of the remains of these creatures, called *Australopithecus ramidus*, is 4.5 million years. "These 4.5 million years are pronounced in one of our words and written down very quickly and easily. However, this is a huge deadline. Especially compared to human life. Attention is drawn to that the ancient traces of mankind were found mainly in the regions of Africa and Asia.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The way of life of primitive people, who for millions of years lived only prepared by nature, developed from the bottom up, albeit very slowly¹. Because man was endowed with such high abilities as intellect, contemplation and reasoning, which were not given to other beings. Therefore, a person with such divine abilities could not live in wildness and lack of meaning, like other creatures. Both divinely and scientifically, man was doomed to develop differently from other beings. There have been many moments in the life of mankind that have led to fundamental turns and radical changes. Of these, the main and most important is determined by the fact that the elements of social relations are formed in the marriage of people. From the point of view of the development of the human race, *Homo sapiens* was practically a social being even at the time of its appearance. After all, it has always been preferable for individuals to live in social groups and alone. At the same time, people began to live

¹ Салимов Б. Л., Мардиев С., Тохиров Ж. Ш. (2022). ТРАНСПОРТ ВА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ТИЗИМЛАРИ ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ АЖРАЛМАС ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ СИФАТИДА. Журнал комплексного образования и исследований , 1 (6), 68–73.

in accordance with certain procedures². The end of doing what they like has come, and people have learned to curb their biological, physical, hysterical and other needs. Such moral norms as shame and conscience, honor, love for a couple, feelings of childhood and fatherhood were formed. Over the centuries, a number of important principles for improving social relations have been developed. These principles, which laid the foundation for the current shape of social relations, opened up a completely new era in people's lives³. The life of these people was completely different from the life of people consisting of primitive bands who lived in herds. They could not be satisfied with what nature gives them, like their predecessors. They were not satisfied with the resurrection day. By discovering animal husbandry and agriculture, they were able to reproduce, recycle and adapt the blessings of nature to themselves. Dependence on nature gave way to the principle of using nature. And the gradual development of handicraft industries led to significant shifts in the family marriage of people. This ultimately laid the foundation for the emergence of an important need that is necessary within the framework of social relations⁴. This need is the need of people to first interact with each other, then with families, seeds, then with tribes, states and, at the very end, with regions or create ways of communication,

² Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022) ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ВА ТРАНСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TSTU Conference 1), 403-407.

³ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Толмасбек Анвар Ўғли Шодмонов, Улуғбек Жеткербай Ўғли Уразбаев (2022). МАМЛАКАТНИНГ БАРҚАРОР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАБ БЕРИШДА ЙЎЛЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 309-314.

⁴ Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich. The Importance of Sea Transport in the Communication System. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2023. Volume 2 Issue 1, 272-275. |

that is, a system of communication. From the point of view of the dictionary, the expression communication means such concepts as a communication path, path, communication and exchange. The term "communication" is commonly used in two different ways: first, in road and transport infrastructure; the second - in the field of the information system. These two areas differ from each other in essence and content. In our scientific work, we will focus on the first direction - communications related to road transport infrastructure⁵.

As the human intellect grew and functioned as a conscious being, the range of its material and spiritual needs also expanded. Now, in order to satisfy these needs, people began to lack activities on the scale of their own clan and tribe. When people realized that in addition to the place where they lived, there are other lands, and other peoples live in them, they developed a passion to visit these places and establish communication with the peoples there. To do this, they first had to look for safe and convenient routes that would lead them to these places and ensure their return. We can say that people have coped with this important task. They laid the foundation for communication routes to other regions. This same aspect was the initial factor shaped by communications in the field of road transport. They found paths leading to other lands, and those who followed these paths became the smartest among the people of that time⁶. Since at that time no compasses were created that would determine North,

⁵ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

⁶ Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich. The Importance of Sea Transport in the Communication System. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2023. Volume 2 Issue 1, 272-275.

South, East and West, there were no geographical maps that would show where the deserts, mountains, rivers or seas are, and where these rivers will flow, and where the seas will last. It was also out of the question that various signs and indications were installed along the roads. In those days, everything depended on the phenomena of nature, as well as on the quick wit and wit of the guides. The guides found their way by looking at the exit and sunset of the day, looking at the alignment of the stars at night and viewing other natural phenomena, as well as memorizing the places they walked. There were also mistakes and miscalculations in this process, and their contributions were sometimes heavy. Therefore, the question of returning to the homes of those who jumped on a long journey also aroused suspicion.

It should be noted that the search for ways to leave and arrive in other countries, although at first it began simply with interest, fanaticism, later his goals and deadlines changed. These goals ranged from simple to complex, depending on the demands of social relationships. The role of science and knowledge intensity, a product of human intelligence, was great in this process. From a scientific point of view, in the development of road communication, the importance of science was significant in solving all existing social problems⁷, including the problems of communication, that is, scientism.

Over the years, these factors have served as an important basis for the development of the road communication system. It can be said that these aspects

⁷ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022) ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ВА ТРАНСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TSTU Conference 1), 403-407.

complemented each other and sometimes existed in an octagonal state. For example, when we get acquainted with the history of martial arts in the past, we become witnesses to the fact that before the start of military, political conflicts between states, communication routes were opened between them and diplomatic relations were established, trade was carried out. Already caravans that went to foreign lands, merchants, in addition to their main work, were also engaged in the work of delivering information, spying to their rulers. But in any case, the opening of lines of communication with other countries, the establishment of cooperation in various fields have acquired a progressive significance in the life of peoples⁸.

As lines of communication between regions were opened, the number of people passing through it increased over time. Over the years, centuries, these roads have become the ones they use all the time. In particular, the Asian continent is considered to be the area where ancient roads originated. Historical sources indicate that "one of the ancient caravan trade routes was called the Cursed Road. This road was discovered in the 3rd-2nd millennium BC. The fact that the road was called the Cursed Road was the reason for the transportation of the precious cursed stone from this road. It was also called Lojuward. The "cursed road" started on the Pamir Mountain and passed through Iran, Mesopotamia and Egypt. Objects made from cursed stones were even found in the tombs (pyramids) of the Egyptian

⁸ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Толмасбек Анвар Ўғли Шодмонов, Улуғбек Жеткербай Ўғли Уразбаев (2022). МАМЛАКАТНИНГ БАРҚАРОР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАБ БЕРИШДА ЙЎЛЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 309-314.

pharaohs⁹.

Another of the famous ancient trade routes is the so-called "Royal Route". It was founded and controlled by the kings of Iran. The Shah Road is bi-directional, with the first linking various cities along the Mediterranean to Iran, while the second runs through Iran and Bactria to the Altai and India.

Records and material monuments of the past indicate that between the Ancient East and the West there was a "Pasture Road", which was considered the Northern Trade Route, passing through the vast expanses that connected the European territories of modern northern China, Mongolia, Siberia, the central part of Russia, Kazakhstan, where nomadic peoples lived. Physical evidence found in settlements on these lands confirms that these territories were interconnected. This "Pasture Road" with thousands of years of history is designated as in the Chinese manabas ("Tsavyuan Lu"). The nomadic pastoral peoples who lived along this road used this route in trade. There is also information that they exchanged various items made by them from precious metals and stones for various goods carried by merchants, including silk fabrics¹⁰. By the way, silk fabrics from China to the West were also transported along this route. But at the same time, it is wrong to consider this route as one of the directions of the "Great Silk Road" or to confuse them with

⁹ Салимов Б. Л., Мардиев С., Тохиров Ж. Ш. (2022). ТРАНСПОРТ ВА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ТИЗИМЛАРИ ИЖТИМОЙИЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ АЖРАЛМАС ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ СИФАТИДА. Журнал комплексного образования и исследований , 1 (6), 68–73.

¹⁰ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). САНОАТ, ФАН-ТЕХНИКА ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ТАБИАТ, ЖАМИЯТ ВА ИНСОНИЯТ ҲАЁТИ БИЛАН ДИАЛЕКТИК АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 351-358.

each other. Because they are considered separate roads. The conclusion contained in this content has also been endorsed by a number of Chinese scholars.

CONCLUSIONS

The establishment of regular communications and trade routes between countries, connecting them with each other, has also changed the intellect of people, worldview, and attitude towards the environment. As can be seen from the above quotation, the first caravan trade routes appeared in Asia, and these roads covered most of the continent. The presence of these roads caused positive changes in the socio-economic, cultural and educational life of the Asian peoples. He influenced the formation and development of the principles of statehood. The emergence of a trading system, which is the basis of economic relations, is also closely related precisely to the methods of communication¹¹. In this case, trading was initially carried out in the form of a swap, and later in the form of coins made from metals such as gold, silver, in the form of a monetary instrument. The discovery of money and the beginning of its use, however, subsequently led to unprecedented consequences within the framework of social relations. The increased interest in money and other material goods led to the formation of classes, subjects of social relations: classes and categories that have been a constant companion of mankind for the next millennia. And the presence of such is

¹¹ Салимов Б. Л., Мардиев С., Тохиров Ж. Ш. (2022). ТРАНСПОРТ ВА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ТИЗИМЛАРИ ИЖТИМОЙИ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ АЖРАЛМАС ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ СИФАТИДА. Журнал комплексного образования и исследований , 1 (6), 68–73.

the basis for the fact that the urgent problem of ensuring social justice among them is always on the agenda.

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